

Assessing the Openness of Scholarly Publications on Sustainable Development Goal “Quality Education” in India: A Data Carpentry Analysis

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Abstract

The Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) established by the United Nations (UN) serve as a global framework for peace, encompassing 17 goals, including SDG-4, which focuses on Quality Education. India, as a UN member, has prioritized these goals. SDG-4 ensures inclusive access to quality education, aligning with India's efforts to enhance its education system. Despite numerous studies on SDGs, there is a gap in understanding the openness of publications related to these goals, particularly in the Indian context. This study addresses this gap by examining the openness of SDG-4-related scholarly publications in India. Using Scopus data from 2015 to 2022, this study collected scholarly publications related to SDG-4. OpenRefine, OpenAlex, and Unpaywall were utilized to assess open access (OA) status, licenses, repository presence, publication locations, and self-archiving efforts. The study analyzed 1,147 publications to determine their accessibility and licensing status. Among the examined publications, 25.89% were in mixed OA routes. Gold OA emerged as the dominant open-access route, with significant contributions in 2020 and 2022. The study observed similar open-access trends in both Unpaywall and OpenAlex databases. Approximately 33.3% of the publications were in OA format. CC-BY licenses were predominant, ensuring legal and ethical use of scholarly content. A considerable portion of Green OA publications were accessible in institutional repositories, reflecting proactive self-archiving by authors and institutions. Open-access publications, especially Gold OA, were dispersed across multiple locations, enhancing their accessibility. Authors actively engaged in self-archiving, with institutional repositories playing a pivotal role.

Keywords: Sustainable Development Goal; Quality Education; Openness; Open Access Publication; Unpaywall; OpenAlex; OpenRefine; Data Carpentry.

1. Introduction

In November 2015, United Nations (UN) member countries adopted the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs). This global agenda serves as a blueprint for peace and priorities for both people and the earth, encompassing 17 goals and 169 targets. Similarly, India has also embraced and endorsed the UN's SDGs. The Indian government consistently focuses on achieving all these goals and targets, recognizing the importance of all 17 goals for human sustainability. SDG-4, titled “Quality Education,” ensures inclusive and equitable access to quality education for all. India, being the world’s third-largest education system in terms of students (Sheikh, 2017), implemented the “Right to Education Act” on April 1, 2010, stipulating free education for all children within the age group of 6-14 years (Cheney et al., 2005; Gupta & Gupta, 2012). To enhance education quality, the Government of India has enacted numerous commissions and bills at the central level. State Governments have also framed education policies in alignment with the Government of India to improve education quality.

Salvia et al. (2019) examined global research trends related to SDGs, measuring both global and local issues. Researchers such as Hassan et al. (2014) and Salvia et al. (2019) focused on scientific publications related to global SDGs using bibliometric approaches. In Africa, Gyimah et al. (2023) explored SDG publications' citations, trending topics, journals, authors, and keywords over seven years. Scholars like Herrera-Calderon et al. (2021) delved into specific SDGs, such as SDG-2 ("Zero Hunger"), analyzing related scholarly publications, annual production, leading institutions, journals, and publishers through bibliometric approaches. Health-related SDG-3 ("Good Health and Well-being") has also been extensively studied using various methods (Addo-Atuah et al., 2020; Fullman et al., 2017; Lim et al., 2016; Lozano et al., 2018; Sweileh, 2020). González García et al. (2020) examined quality education-related publications in Web of Science and Scopus, analyzing variables such as year of publication, document type, indexation area, periodical publications, productive authors, institutions, countries, languages, most cited articles, and keywords. Similarly, Roy et al. (2022) investigated recent trends in SDG-6 ("Clean Water and Sanitation") research using a scientometric approach. Guo & Peng (2023) explored SDG-11 ("Sustainable Cities and Communities") related scholarly publications using Citespace and ArcGIS. However, there is a lack of studies regarding the openness of scholarly publications related to sustainable development goals.

Considering this gap, the present study examines the openness of SDG-4 ("Quality of Education") related publications in the Indian context. This goal comprises ten targets aimed at fostering quality education and lifelong learning. Scholarly publication openness depends on reader rights, re-use rights, copyrights, author posting rights, automatic posting, and machine readability (SPARC et al., 2013). This study attempts to determine openness based on open-access publications, considering reader rights, license use, automatic posting, and author posting rights. Scholarly publication data were obtained using the data carpentry tool OpenRefine, which retrieved information related to open-access publications through REST API calls from OpenAlex and Unpaywall.

2. Literature Review

Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) are currently a prominent global issue. Consequently, various types of reviews, including narrative, critical overview, systematic, meta-analysis, bibliometric, and scientometric analyses, have been conducted. Authors have utilized different software and applications for data analysis and interpretation in their research.

Diksha & Chakravarty (2022) examined global research trends on sustainable development goals using Bibliometrix R and Scopus data from 1996 to 2020. They analyzed 1,872 documents, assessing bibliometric indicators, research publication growth, trending topics, prominent sources, and prolific authors, and validated Lotka's law. Similarly, Sianes et al. (2022) explored the impact of SDGs on academic research through a scientometric approach, analyzing 5,281 research articles from the Web of Science database (2015-2022). The study revealed insights into affiliated institutions, thematic coverage, and academic contributions' relations. A comprehensive study by Zhu & Hua (2017) utilized Web of Science data (1987-2015), comprising 59,926 records from 32 languages, 49 countries, and 149 research areas. They found China to be the most productive country, followed by the USA, UK, Australia, and Germany. Alfirić et al. (2023) explored the productivity and impact of SDGs in academic research based on 1,511

documents (15,588 citations) from Scopus (2017-2022), using SciVal tool. Their analysis encompassed document formats, leading countries, subject categories, research output impact, intellectual structure, and keyword co-occurrence map.

Recognizing the significance of all seventeen SDGs for human development, scholars have focused on specific goals. Herrera-Calderon et al. (2021) examined Pacific Alliance's "Zero Hunger" scholarly publications using bibliometric approaches, while Prieto-Jiménez et al. (2021) analyzed SDG-4 (Quality Education) publications and related topics. Guo & Peng (2023) explored SDG-11 (Sustainable Cities and Communities) publications using bibliometric and spatial auto-correlation methods. Farrukh et al. (2020) studied sustainable development journals (1993-2019) analyzing publication structures, co-citation, bibliographic coupling, authors, and countries. Chen & Olijhoek (2016) evaluated the openness of 1,005 scholarly journals using the OAS evaluation tool, and Melero et al. (2017) assessed the openness of Spanish scholarly journals based on access and rights.

3. Objectives of the study

The present study aims to achieve the following objectives:

- a) To determine the growth of OA publications over the specified period.
- b) To examine the use of licenses in OA publications and various documentary sources.
- c) To identify the availability of OA publications in repositories throughout the specified period.
- d) To focus on the number of publication locations, and
- e) To assess the extent of self-archiving of Green OA in institutional repositories.

4. Methodology

Primary data collection

This study collected data related to SDG-4, specifically focusing on "quality education," from the extensive bibliographic and citation database Scopus. It utilized a pre-generated string for SDG goals. The research examined scholarly publications affiliated with India for the past eight years, from 2015 to 2022. The provided string was employed for data collection using the "TITLE-ABS-KEY" search criteria, including keywords such as school, education, educational, school attendance, school enrollment, inclusive education, educational inequality, education quality, and others. Data related to health literacy were excluded. A total of 1,147 scholarly publication records were extracted from Scopus. Table 1 displays the publications' open/closed access status according to the Scopus data. Among these 1,147 scholarly publications, 25.89% (n=297) of documents are present in different mixed OA routes. Upon uploading the dataset to OpenRefine for data cleaning, it was noted that 196 documents lack a Digital Object Identifier (DOI), as shown in Table 2.

Development of a secondary dataset

The current study assessed the extent of openness in scholarly publications related to SDG-4, which focuses on the quality of education. This investigation involved examining reader rights, re-use rights, and author posting rights associated with these publications. Additionally, the open-access status was evaluated using REST API calls to both OpenAlex and Unpaywall.

OpenAlex, recognized as one of the largest comprehensive repositories of scholarly publications, provides access to a vast collection of 240 million works and 1.9 billion citations, which are freely and fully accessible without any restrictions (Priem et al., 2022). Through OpenRefine, a total of 951 DOI publication queries were submitted via REST API calls to OpenAlex, resulting in 910 responses (95.69%) received from the platform, as shown in Table 3.

Table 1: Open/Closed Access Status of Publications

Year	Total	Closed Access	Open Access	% of OA	OA Categories						
					Green OA	Gold OA	Gold, Green	Hybrid Gold	Hybrid GO, GR	Bronze	Bronze, Green
2015	79	64	15	23.44	3	3	3	--	1	3	2
2016	102	83	19	22.89	4	1	6	1	1	5	1
2017	92	69	23	33.33	10	6	2	--	2	3	--
2018	112	82	30	36.59	9	1	12	--	2	4	2
2019	170	127	43	33.86	5	6	13	--	--	18	1
2020	150	107	43	40.19	5	11	11	2	1	11	2
2021	197	144	53	36.81	7	14	10	3	2	13	4
2022	245	174	71	40.80	5	24	18	7	5	8	4
Grand Total	1,147	850	297	25.89	48	66	75	13	14	65	16

Table 2: Publications with DOI

Year	Total Publications	Publications with DOI	% of Publications with DOI
2015	79	61	77.22
2016	102	75	73.53
2017	92	75	81.52
2018	112	96	85.71
2019	170	129	75.88
2020	150	118	78.67
2021	197	169	85.79
2022	245	228	93.06
Total	1,147	951	82.91

Table 3: Use of REST API to fetch the OA status of the publication.

SL	Use of REST API	The number of queries sends	The number of responses received
1	"https://api.openalex.org/works/https://doi.org/" + DOI	951 DOI Publications	910 (95.69%)
2	"https://api.unpaywall.org/v2/" + DOI + "?email=own email id"		907 (95.37%)

Similarly, Unpaywall, another prominent bibliographic storehouse of open-access scholarly publications, offers access to over 47,918,396 publications (as of August 12, 2023) at no cost, accessible via REST API calls. In this study, 951 DOI publications were submitted, leading to 907 responses (95.37%) received from Unpaywall (Table 3). It is worth mentioning that

documents lacking a DOI were excluded from the analysis, and consequently, OpenAlex and Unpaywall did not provide responses for these publications.

5. Data Analysis

a) Open Access Publications

Upon examining the Unpaywall and OpenAlex responses (JSON data sets), we observed that both databases provided nearly identical data. Table 4 illustrates the open-access status of scholarly publications on SDG-4 according to Unpaywall. Unpaywall indicated that 67.14% (n=609) of scholarly publications were available in closed access, while 32.86% (n=298) were in open access (OA) format, further categorized into four OA routes. Among OA categories, the highest number of OA publications (180 publications, 60.40% of total OA) were published in Gold OA, followed by Green OA (47 publications), Bronze OA (43 publications), and Hybrid OA (28 publications). According to Table 4, the highest number of OA publications (n=71) appeared in the year 2022, with the highest share of OA publications (39.09%) observed in the year 2020.

Table 4: Status of Open/Closed Access (based on Unpaywall)

Year	Total Pub.	Closed Access	Open Access	% of OA	OA Categories			
					Green	Gold	Hybrid	Bronze
2015	59	44	15	25.42	3	7	1	4
2016	71	52	19	26.76	4	9	2	4
2017	71	48	23	32.39	10	10	2	1
2018	94	64	30	31.91	9	15	2	4
2019	127	83	44	34.65	4	34	--	6
2020	110	67	43	39.09	5	27	3	8
2021	159	106	53	33.33	7	34	6	6
2022	216	145	71	32.87	5	44	12	10
Grand Total	907	609	298	32.86	47	180	28	43

Table 5: Status of Open/Closed Access (based on OpenAlex)

Year	Total Pub.	Closed Access	Open Access	% of OA	OA Categories			
					Green	Gold	Hybrid	Bronze
2015	59	45	14	23.73	3	7	1	3
2016	71	52	19	26.76	4	9	2	4
2017	71	48	23	32.39	10	10	2	1
2018	95	64	31	32.63	9	15	2	5
2019	126	80	46	36.51	3	33	--	10
2020	111	66	45	40.54	8	27	3	7
2021	162	107	55	33.95	7	35	6	7
2022	215	145	70	32.56	6	44	12	8
Grand Total	910	607	303	33.3	50	180	28	45

Table 5 presents the closed/open access status of publications based on OpenAlex. A total of 951 DOI publications were submitted via OpenRefine, resulting in 910 responses from OpenAlex.

Upon analyzing the datasets, we found that 66.7% (n=607) of publications were available in closed access, and 33.3% (n=303) were in open access form. Comparing Tables 4 and 5, it is evident that both databases (Unpaywall & OpenAlex) showed similar numbers of Gold OA and Hybrid OA publications. The proportion of open-access publications in these databases is nearly identical, with no significant differences. According to Table 5, the highest number of OA publications (n=70) was recorded in the year 2022, with the highest share of OA publications (40.54%) observed in the year 2020. The open-access status of publications obtained from Unpaywall closely aligns with the open-access status of publications obtained from OpenAlex.

b) Use of Licenses in OA Publications

Table 6 presents the licensing scenario of OA publications retrieved for SDG-4. The study observed seven types of licenses in OA publications from both databases (OpenAlex & Unpaywall). From Table 6, it can be seen that Unpaywall-based publications (n=176, 59.06%) have shown a higher number of licenses than OpenAlex-based publications (n=162, 53.47%). Among the OA licenses, the most commonly used license is CC-BY for both databases (n=92, 52.27% of total licensing publications in Unpaywall; n=82, 50.62% in OpenAlex), followed by CC-BY-NC-ND (n=40, 22.73% in Unpaywall; n=39, 24.07% in OpenAlex), CC-BY-NC, CC-BY-NC-SA, CC-BY-SA, and Public Domain.

Table 6: Use of License in OA Publications

Type of License	OpenAlex Publications	Unpaywall Publications
PD	1	1
CC-BY	82	92
CC-BY-SA	2	2
CC-BY-NC	20	22
CC-BY-NC-SA	17	19
CC-BY-NC-ND	39	40
Elsevier-specific: OA user license	1	0
Total Licenses	162 (53.47%)	176 (59.06%)
Without Licenses	141 (46.53%)	122 (40.94%)
Total OA Publications	303	298

From Table 6, it is evident that 53.47% (n=162) of publications from OpenAlex and 59.06% (n=176) of publications from Unpaywall are published with legal licenses. Figure 1 displays the licensing scenario of OA publications within OA categories for both databases. From Fig. 1, it is observed that all Hybrid OA publications from both databases are published with legal licenses. According to OpenAlex data, all Green OA publications are published without legal licenses. Similarly, all Bronze OA publications from Unpaywall are published without legal licenses. In the case of Green OA publications from Unpaywall, 14.89% (n=7) of publications are published with legal licenses, while the majority of publications are without legal licenses. A very low percentage of Bronze OA publications from OpenAlex have legal licenses. The majority of Gold OA publications have legal licenses in both databases.

Table 7 displays documentary formats and their use of licenses in different OA categories (based on OpenAlex data). The study observed nine documentary formats: Article, Review, Conference

Paper, Book, Book Chapter, Editorial, Erratum, Letter, and Note. Upon analyzing the document category "Article," it was found that 57.68% of articles (n=139) are published with a license. Similarly, 66.67% of "Notes" are published with a license. All Errata are published in Bronze OA without any licensing. From Table 7, it is evident that all Green OA publications are published without any license, while all Hybrid OA publications are published with licenses. The majority of Bronze OA publications (97.78%) are published without any license, while the majority of Gold OA publications (73.89%) are published with legal licenses.

Fig. 1: Use of Licenses in OA Categories in OpenAlex & Unpaywall

Table 7: Use of Licenses in Different Document Types & OA Categories (based on OpenAlex)

Types of Documents	Green OA		Gold OA		Hybrid OA		Bronze OA		Total	
	WL	WOL	WL	WOL	WL	WOL	WL	WOL	WL	WOL
Article (241)	0	30	116	37	22	0	1	35	139	102
Review (21)	0	5	9	4	1	0	0	2	10	11
Conference Paper (14)	0	2	4	5	2	0	0	1	6	8
Book (9)	0	8	0	0	1	0	0	0	1	8
Book Chapter (5)	0	3	1	0	1	0	0	0	2	3
Editorial (4)	0	1	1	0	0	0	0	2	1	3
Erratum (3)	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	3	0	3
Letter (3)	0	1	0	1	1	0	0	0	1	2
Note (3)	0	0	2	0	0	0	0	1	2	1
Total (303)	0	50	133	47	28	0	1	44	162	141
Percentage	0	100%	73.89%	26.11%	100%	0	2.22%	97.78%	53.47%	46.53%

Legends: WL = With License, WOL = Without License

c) Open Access Publications in Repositories

The study examined the full-text availability of OA publications in different repositories based on OpenAlex data. Among the 303 OA publications, 49.83% (n=151) are available in full-text and accessible in various repositories. Overall, 86% of Green OA publications (n=43 out of 50) are accessible in different repositories, followed by 60.71% (n=17 out of 28) of Hybrid OA publications, 43.33% (n=78 out of 180) of Gold OA publications, and 28.89% (n=13 out of 45) of Bronze OA publications. Figure 2 illustrates the availability of OA publications in different repositories over the years. Throughout the study period, all Green OA publications were accessible in different repositories for the years 2015, 2016, 2020, 2021, and 2022. In 2017, all Bronze OA publications were available in various repositories. Regarding Hybrid OA publications, all of them were accessible in the years 2015, 2017, and 2018. Gold OA publications were also accessible in different repositories but never reached 100% availability due to the nature of their publication.

Fig. 2: Open Access Publications Availability in Repositories

d) Location of Publications

The study investigated the location status of publications, considering various publication sources such as journal sites, publisher sites, and publisher groups, where these documents are stored or published. Table 8 presents the location status of closed/open access publications. According to Table 8, it is observed that 92.09% of closed access publications are available at one location (journal/publisher/database vendor site), while 7.58% of publications are available in two locations. For OA publications, 41.25% are available at one location, and 58.75% are accessible in more than one location. In the case of Green OA publications, 46% are present in two locations, while 12% are found at one location. The majority of Green OA publications (88%) are available in multiple locations. Gold OA publications are spread across nine locations, with the highest share (43.33%) present in one location. Overall, the majority of Gold OA publications (56.67%) are available at multiple locations. In Hybrid OA, the highest number of publications (42.86%) is available at two locations, while 35.71% are found at one location. For

Bronze OA, 68.89% of publications are available at one location, with the remaining publications present at multiple locations.

Table 8: Publication’s Location Status

Publication Groups	Location of Publications								Unknown	Total
	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	9		
Closed Access	559 (92.09%)	46 (7.58%)	1 (0.16%)	0	0	0	0	0	1 (0.16%)	607 (100%)
Open Access	125 (41.25%)	73 (24.09%)	44 (14.52%)	36 (11.88%)	14 (4.62%)	7 (2.31%)	2 (0.66%)	2 (0.66%)	0	303 (100%)
Green OA	6 (12%)	23 (46%)	11 (22%)	8 (16%)	2 (4%)	0	0	0	0	50 (100%)
Gold OA	78 (43.33%)	33 (18.33%)	21 (11.67%)	26 (14.44%)	11 (6.11%)	7 (3.89%)	2 (1.11%)	2 (1.11%)	0	180 (100%)
Hybrid OA	10 (35.71%)	12 (42.86%)	5 (17.86%)	1 (3.57%)	0	0	0	0	0	28 (100%)
Bronze OA	31 (68.89%)	5 (11.11%)	7 (15.56%)	1 (2.22%)	1 (2.22%)	0	0	0	0	45 (100%)

e) Self-archiving of Green OA in Repositories

The study examined the self-archiving rights of authors using data from OpenAlex. OpenAlex provides the self-archiving status of Green OA publications. During the study period, a total of 50 Green OA publications were published by Indian authors, out of which 78% were found in 20 institutional repositories worldwide.

Fig. 3: Self-archiving of Green OA in Repositories

Figure 3 illustrates the self-archiving of Green OA publications in institutional repositories. A total of 39 Green OA publications were self-archived in various repositories. The highest self-archiving of Green OA publications was observed in the year 2017 (8 self-archived publications), followed by the years 2021 (7 self-archived publications), and 2020 & 2022 (6 self-archived

publications). Among the self-archived 39 Green OA publications, they were stored in multiple repositories, with the top three institutional repositories being: i) European Bioinformatics Institute (5 Green OA, 12.82% of total self-archived publications), ii) Federal Reserve Bank of St. Louis (5 Green OA, 12.82%), and iii) Cornell University (4 Green OA, 10.26%). A total of 43.59% of Green OA publications (n=17 out of 39) were found in these top three institutional repositories.

6. Conclusion

This study focused on the openness of scholarly publications related to Sustainable Development Goal 4 (SDG-4) in India, emphasizing Quality Education. It explored the accessibility, licensing, and repository presence of these publications. Using data from OpenAlex and Unpaywall, the study found a significant portion accessible via open access, primarily through Gold OA, followed by Green OA, Bronze OA, and Hybrid OA. The years 2020 and 2022 witnessed increased open-access publications. Legal licenses, especially CC-BY, were prevalent, and Green OA publications were actively self-archived in institutional repositories. Closed-access publications were confined to specific sites, while open-access ones, especially Gold OA, were widely available. The study highlights the progress in scholarly publications' openness, promoting a more equitable and collaborative global knowledge ecosystem in alignment with SDG-4 and broader Sustainable Development Goals.

References

- Addo-Atuah, J., Senhaji-Tomza, B., Ray, D., Basu, P., Loh, F.-H. (Ellen), & Owusu-Daaku, F. (2020). Global health research partnerships in the context of the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs). *Research in Social and Administrative Pharmacy*, 16(11), 1614–1618. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.sapharm.2020.08.015>
- Alfirević, N., Malešević Perović, L., & Mihaljević Kosor, M. (2023). Productivity and Impact of Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs)-Related Academic Research: A Bibliometric Analysis. *Sustainability*, 15(9), Article 9. <https://doi.org/10.3390/su15097434>
- Chen, X., & Olijhoek, T. (2016). Measuring the Degrees of Openness of Scholarly Journals with the Open Access Spectrum (OAS) Evaluation Tool. *Serials Review*, 42(2), 108–115. <https://doi.org/10.1080/00987913.2016.1182672>
- Cheney, G. R., Ruzzi, B. B., & Muralidharan, K. (2005). A profile of the Indian education system. *Prepared for the New Commission on the Skills of the American Workforce*, 228–253.
- Diksha, D., & Chakravarty, R. (2022). Global Trends in the Research Output on Sustainable Development Goals: A Bibliometric Analysis Using Bibliometrix R-Tool. In *Futuristic Trends for Sustainable Development and Sustainable Ecosystems* (pp. 27–47). IGI Global. <https://doi.org/10.4018/978-1-6684-4225-8.ch002>
- Farrukh, M., Meng, F., Raza, A., & Tahir, M. S. (2020). Twenty-seven years of Sustainable Development Journal: A bibliometric analysis. *Sustainable Development*, 28(6), 1725–1737. <https://doi.org/10.1002/sd.2120>

- Fullman, N., Barber, R. M., Abajobir, A. A., Abate, K. H., Abbafati, C., Abbas, K. M., Abd-Allah, F., Abdulkader, R. S., Abdulle, A. M., Abera, S. F., Aboyans, V., Abu-Raddad, L. J., Abu-Rmeileh, N. M. E., Adedeji, I. A., Adetokunboh, O., Afshin, A., Agrawal, A., Agrawal, S., Ahmad Kiadaliri, A., ... Murray, C. J. L. (2017). Measuring progress and projecting attainment on the basis of past trends of the health-related Sustainable Development Goals in 188 countries: An analysis from the Global Burden of Disease Study 2016. *The Lancet*, 390(10100), 1423–1459. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0140-6736\(17\)32336-X](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0140-6736(17)32336-X)
- González García, E., Colomo Magaña, E., & Cívico Ariza, A. (2020). Quality Education as a Sustainable Development Goal in the Context of 2030 Agenda: Bibliometric Approach. *Sustainability*, 12(15), Article 15. <https://doi.org/10.3390/su12155884>
- Guo, J., & Peng, X. (2023). Status of research on Sustainable Development Goal 11: A visual analysis using citespace and ArcGIS. *International Journal of Sustainable Development & World Ecology*, 0(0), 1–13. <https://doi.org/10.1080/13504509.2023.2190177>
- Gupta, D., & Gupta, N. (2012). Higher education in India: Structure, statistics and challenges. *Journal of Education and Practice*, 3(2). https://www.academia.edu/download/13141479/11.Higher_Education_in_India_Structure__Statistics_and_Challenges.pdf
- Gyimah, P., Appiah, K. O., & Appiagyei, K. (2023). Seven years of United Nations’ sustainable development goals in Africa: A bibliometric and systematic methodological review. *Journal of Cleaner Production*, 395, 136422. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jclepro.2023.136422>
- Hassan, S.-U., Haddawy, P., & Zhu, J. (2014). A bibliometric study of the world’s research activity in sustainable development and its sub-areas using scientific literature. *Scientometrics*, 99(2), 549–579. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11192-013-1193-3>
- Herrera-Calderon, O., Yuli-Posadas, R. Á., Peña-Rojas, G., Andía-Ayme, V., Hañari-Quispe, R. D., & Gregorio-Chaviano, O. (2021). A bibliometric analysis of the scientific production related to “zero hunger” as a sustainable development goal: Trends of the pacific alliance towards 2030. *Agriculture & Food Security*, 10(1), 34. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s40066-021-00315-8>
- Lim, S. S., Allen, K., Bhutta, Z. A., Dandona, L., Forouzanfar, M. H., Fullman, N., Gething, P. W., Goldberg, E. M., Hay, S. I., Holmberg, M., Kinfu, Y., Kutz, M. J., Larson, H. J., Liang, X., Lopez, A. D., Lozano, R., McNellan, C. R., Mokdad, A. H., Mooney, M. D., ... Murray, C. J. L. (2016). Measuring the health-related Sustainable Development Goals in 188 countries: A baseline analysis from the Global Burden of Disease Study 2015. *The Lancet*, 388(10053), 1813–1850. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0140-6736\(16\)31467-2](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0140-6736(16)31467-2)

- Lozano, R., Fullman, N., Abate, D., Abay, S. M., Abbafati, C., Abbasi, N., Abbastabar, H., Abd-Allah, F., Abdela, J., Abdelalim, A., Abdel-Rahman, O., Abdi, A., Abdollahpour, I., Abdulkader, R. S., Abebe, N. D., Abebe, Z., Abeje, A. N., Abera, S. F., Abil, O. Z., ... Murray, C. J. L. (2018). Measuring progress from 1990 to 2017 and projecting attainment to 2030 of the health-related Sustainable Development Goals for 195 countries and territories: A systematic analysis for the Global Burden of Disease Study 2017. *The Lancet*, 392(10159), 2091–2138. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0140-6736\(18\)32281-5](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0140-6736(18)32281-5)
- Melero, R., Laakso, M., & Navas-Fernández, M. (2017). Openness of Spanish scholarly journals as measured by access and rights. *Learned Publishing*, 30(2), 143–155. <https://doi.org/10.1002/leap.1095>
- Priem, J., Piwowar, H., & Orr, R. (2022). OpenAlex: A fully-open index of scholarly works, authors, venues, institutions, and concepts. *arXiv Preprint arXiv:2205.01833*.
- Prieto-Jiménez, E., López-Catalán, L., López-Catalán, B., & Domínguez-Fernández, G. (2021). Sustainable Development Goals and Education: A Bibliometric Mapping Analysis. *Sustainability*, 13(4), Article 4. <https://doi.org/10.3390/su13042126>
- Roy, A., Basu, A., Su, Y., Li, Y., & Dong, X. (2022). Understanding Recent Trends in Global Sustainable Development Goal 6 Research: Scientometric, Text Mining and an Improved Framework for Future Research. *Sustainability*, 14(4), Article 4. <https://doi.org/10.3390/su14042208>
- Salvia, A. L., Leal Filho, W., Brandli, L. L., & Griebeler, J. S. (2019). Assessing research trends related to Sustainable Development Goals: Local and global issues. *Journal of Cleaner Production*, 208, 841–849. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jclepro.2018.09.242>
- Sheikh, Y. A. (2017). Higher Education in India: Challenges and Opportunities. *Journal of Education and Practice*, 8(1), 39–42.
- Sianes, A., Vega-Muñoz, A., Tirado-Valencia, P., & Ariza-Montes, A. (2022). Impact of the Sustainable Development Goals on the academic research agenda. A scientometric analysis. *PLOS ONE*, 17(3), e0265409. <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0265409>
- SPARC, PLOS, & OASPA. (2013). *HowOpenIsIt: Open Access Spectrum*. https://sparcopen.org/wp-content/uploads/2016/01/hoii_guide_rev4_web.pdf
- Sweileh, W. M. (2020). Bibliometric analysis of scientific publications on “sustainable development goals” with emphasis on “good health and well-being” goal (2015–2019). *Globalization and Health*, 16(1), 68. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s12992-020-00602-2>
- Zhu, J., & Hua, W. (2017). Visualizing the knowledge domain of sustainable development research between 1987 and 2015: A bibliometric analysis. *Scientometrics*, 110(2), 893–914.